

Fullscale Optimization and Fan Design of a Rear BLI Shrouded Propulsor

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The environmental concern on the impact of civil air transportation has become a primary driving force for the research and development towards new technologies that could provide a reduction in the emissions. In the context of civil aircraft transportation, Boundary Layer Ingestion (BLI) is among the most promising solutions. Such architecture is characterized by a high level of integration between the airframe and propulsors, making the design process becomes a major challenge. The present work deals with a complete CFD based design and optimization of a propulsive fuselage concept, both in terms of airframe shape and fan design.

I. Nomenclature

F	=	gauge force
ϕ	=	wall force acting on the drag domain
θ	=	wall force acting on the thrust domain
D_{ref}	=	reference fuselage drag of a non-BLI configuration
NAF	=	net assembly force and
ΔNAF	=	net assembly force referred to the reference drag
PSC	=	power saving coefficient
S_w	=	wall surface area
A	=	flow passage area
k	=	specific heats ratio
R	=	gas constant
T	=	static temperature
T^0	=	total temperature
p	=	static pressure
p^0	=	total pressure
ρ	=	density
M	=	Mach number
Re	=	Reynolds number
V	=	velocity
τ_w	=	wall shear stress
\dot{m}, mfr	=	mass flow rate
π_c, FPR	=	fan total pressure ratio
η_{pol}	=	fan polytropic efficiency
W_{fan}	=	fan shaft power
$W_{\Delta NAF}$	=	ΔNAF useful power
$\eta_{\Delta NAF}$	=	ΔNAF efficiency
$()_{\infty}$	=	generic quantity evaluated at freestream conditions

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- $()_I$ = generic quantity evaluated at the propulsor fan intake section
- $()_E$ = generic quantity evaluated at the propulsor fan exhaust section
- dv = design variables
- BLI = Boundary layer ingestion
- CFD = Computational Fluid Dynamics
- RANS = Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
- WTT = Wind Tunnel Test
- DoE = Design of Experiments
- MOOP = Multi-Objective Optimization Problem

II. Introduction

ATMOSPHERIC emissions from civil aircraft transportation strongly contribute to climate change and degradation of the air quality. Since 1950, the rate of increase of global air transportation is about 5% per year for passenger and 6% per year for freight[1]. CO₂ is the single largest contributor to the anthropogenic greenhouse effect: in 2011, the contribution of global aviation was calculated to be 3.5% of the net anthropogenic effective radiative forcing[2].

In such context, an increasing awareness about the impact of civil air transportation emissions is currently driving a low-carbon technology transition, towards more sustainable propulsion strategies. Boundary layer ingesting systems are one of the most promising solutions, as a closer integration between fuselage and propulsors is considered a key in the achievement of more sustainable architectures.

Multiple BLI layouts have been proposed, such as the propulsive fuselages (PF), rear engines (RE) or distributed fans over blended wing body (BWB) concepts[3]. In this regard, although more integrated solutions as the BWB concepts appear more promising, concepts as the PF are most likely to be implemented within a shorter term due to a relatively small modification requirement to the classic tube and wing airframe. At a more quantitative level, it is apparent that a BLI system design must undergo a refined optimization process in order to get a net benefit in terms of propulsive efficiency.

BLI applications in marine propulsion are quite common, and extensions to aeronautic propulsion have been considered in the past years[4]. At a conceptual level, the key to such technology is the wake filling principle (sketched in Fig. 1): the ingestion of the fuselage low-momentum boundary layer flow provides a re-energizing of the aircraft wake. Thus, a reduction of the momentum deficit is expected. This translates in a reduction of the jet velocity necessary to obtain the desired net force, which eventually increases the propulsive efficiency.

Fig. 1 Conceptual schematics of the wake filling principle.

One of the major challenges in the design process of a BLI system is the quantification of the performance metrics. It is rather intuitive how the close integration between the aircraft and the engine does not permit a clear distinction between thrust and drag[5]. Although such integration provides the possibility for different definitions of thrust and drag, an ambiguity still persists in determining which portion of the airframe contributes to thrust or drag, thus making conventional expressions for the propulsive performance virtually useless.

The determination of a consistent thrust-drag bookkeeping scheme is relevant and cannot follow the conventional momentum conservation approach used for a classic podded engine. Various bookkeeping approaches have been proposed for the conceptual design phase[6] based on momentum or power conservation approaches[7]. Smith[4] bypassed the problem of non-uniqueness in the definition of installed thrust and introduced a power saving coefficient metric (*PSC*) that could quantify the benefits in terms of mechanical power needed to propel an aircraft using a BLI engine with reference on a non-BLI system when both configurations provide a zero net-force balance on an aircraft travelling at a desired Mach number:

$$PSC = \frac{W - W_{BLI}}{W} \Big|_{M_\infty, NAF=0} \quad (1)$$

Other metrics have been used to determine the benefits of a BLI system: Drela[8] introduced a fuel burn metric to quantify the benefits of a boundary layer ingestion layout for the D8.x configurations. In that case, a 33% fuel consumption reduction has been demonstrated with respect to an optimized transport configuration, with benefits coming from drag reduction and the possibility to implement low-sweep wings for reduced structural weight and increased lift coefficient. However, this has been carried out at relatively low Mach number.

A wind tunnel test scale model design of a propulsive fuselage[9, 10] has been carried out by introducing two figures of merit based on a momentum conservation approach: although how a clear distinction between thrust and drag forces cannot be determined, it is also apparent that a force balance can still be valid when considering the overall architecture. The performance accounting has been therefore defined considering the overall airframe force acting on the airframe[9]. As sketched in Fig. 2, the wall forces acting on the drag domain on a generic surface S_w are denoted by ϕ , the ones acting on the thrust domain are denoted with θ , whilst the gauge forces at the intake and exhaust sections of the propulsor are denoted by F . Their components on the streamwise direction \hat{x} can be evaluated as:

$$\phi, \theta = \int_{S_w} [(p - p_\infty) \hat{n} + \vec{\tau}_w] \cdot \hat{x} dS \quad (2)$$

$$F = \int_A [(p - p_\infty) \hat{n} + \rho \vec{V} (\vec{V} \cdot \hat{n})] \cdot \hat{x} dA \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 Airframe forces breakdown: streamwise forces components.

The Net Assembly force can therefore be evaluated as:

$$NAF = (F_E - \theta_{eh} - \theta_{es}) - (F_I + \theta_{ih} + \theta_{is}) - (\phi_{fus} + \phi_{aft} + \phi_{nac} + \phi_{plg}) \quad (4)$$

The *NAF* has been then referred to a reference fuselage drag, which has been provided based on available data on a commercial aircraft:

$$\Delta NAF = NAF - D_{ref} \quad (5)$$

ΔNAF is to be intended as a surrogate of the net propulsive thrust. It takes into account the installation effects of the BLI nacelle and the variations in the fuselage shape with reference to a non-BLI configuration. From the , it has been defined a ΔNAF efficiency, which quantifies the amount of shaft power converted in useful power. The useful power is here related to ΔNAF (the minus sign in Eq. 6 is justified by the fact that the *NAF* has been defined positive in the streamwise direction).

$$\eta_{\Delta NAF} = \frac{-\Delta NAF V_\infty}{W_{fan}} \quad (6)$$

with the fan shaft power being:

$$W_{fan} = \dot{m} (h_E^0 - h_I^0) \quad (7)$$

III. Scope of the Activity

The present work is part of the Clean Sky 2 project SUBLIME (Support Understanding of Boundary Layer Ingestion Model Experiment). The primary aim of the project is to answer some of the uncertainties in the area of BLI, by means of performing an integrated investigation between several wing+fuselage configurations and BLI propulsor concepts. A preliminary design space investigation[9] of a propulsive fuselage concept and a complete design of a wind tunnel test model[10] have been produced. The further step, which is also the scope of the present activity, consists in a complete design of a full scale propulsive fuselage model, with the aim of minimizing the fan inlet flow distortion and maximize the performance (here expressed in terms of $\eta_{\Delta NAF}$). The present work is therefore divided into two primary sections:

- 1) The three-dimensional design optimization of the propulsive fuselage, with the aim of determining the geometric configuration which could maximize the ΔNAF efficiency.
- 2) The conceptual design of a fan operating in the optimised propulsor configuration.

A. Propulsor Design Optimization

The previous design of the WTT model[10] has given some insights on the main geometrical features of a BLI-360 propulsor. Although such model were highly constrained by manufacturing and sizing requirements, it served as a basis for the definition of a workflow and for the determination of appropriate ranges to the design variables.

The BLI360 propulsor design optimization has been carried out by considering two main phases: the first part has concern the definition and optimization of a two-dimensional axialsymmetric geometric model. This served as a baseline for the definition of a three-dimensional shape, which has therefore been optimized. The performance accounting has been defined based on a momentum conservation approach which considers the overall airframe force accounting[9], as summarized in Sec. II.

For both the two-dimensional and three-dimensional design phases, RANS CFD simulations using ANSYS[®] Fluent have been set up for the evaluation of the propulsor performance. In the CFD analyses, a boundary conditions model defined by mass flow outlet/inlet has been used as substitute of an actual fan, in accordance with the preliminary design space investigation[9].

The fan polytropic efficiency η_{pol} has been taken as functional constraint, whilst the fan pressure ratio π_c has been considered as a design variable for the optimization problem.

In such context, the ingested mass flow rate becomes an output parameter of both η_{pol} and π_c , as well as the propulsor cross-sectional areas. Its value cannot therefore be evaluated prior to the CFD analysis. The problem has been solved iteratively by fixing the fan pressure ratio and polytropic efficiency as target values and by defining the BCs mass flow rate and exhaust total temperature as named expressions in the form of:

$$\dot{m}(j+1) = A_E \pi_c p_I^0(j) \sqrt{\frac{k}{R T_I^0(j) \pi_c^{\frac{k-1}{k \eta_{pol}}}} M_E(j) \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_E^2(j)\right)^{\frac{k+1}{2(1-k)}}} \quad (8)$$

$$T_E^0(j+1) = T_I^0(j) \pi_c^{\frac{k-1}{k \eta_{pol}}} \quad (9)$$

The intake section total temperature (mass-average) and total pressure (area-average), as well as the exhaust section Mach number (mass-average) are calculated at the end of each $j - th$ CFD iteration. The mass flow rate and exhaust total temperature at the $(j+1) - th$ iteration are therefore calculated starting from these output values, until convergence of the CFD simulation.

B. Conceptual Fan Design

After the optimisation of the BLI360 configuration, the second phase of the study focused on a conceptual design of a fan rotor providing the required thrust, according to the requirements indicated by the optimisation. The activity tackled a preliminary exploration of a fan operating in the specific BLI environment, characterised by an uneven distribution of inflow parameters due to the boundary layer itself and the fuselage upsweep, introducing total pressure, static pressure, and swirl distortion. The study was far from being a complete design investigation for a BLI distortion tolerant fan, but rather a circumscribed attempt to match the design point requirements through a specific blade definition considering the impact of the BLI from the beginning of the design phase.

While the interaction between fan rotors and incoming distortion has been deeply inquired in the literature, a less consolidated knowledge is available in terms of design procedures for BLI operating fans. The NASA BLI2DTF project

combined CFD-based analyses for design and optimisation of a BLI system, including fan design, simulation, and wind tunnel testing with a mail-slotted nacelle for a hybrid wing body wing [11]. Castillo Pardo [12] described the aerodynamic design of a BLI fan for the aft-mounted propulsor of the CENTRELINE project. The authors started from a baseline geometry for clean inflow and adapted to the BLI inlet profile through blade restaggering, to compensate for the low hub momentum and increased tip incidence. Mennicken [13] employed a throughflow method for fast estimation of fan design attributes under BLI, concluding that distortion-tolerant blades should be conceived with higher tip speed to limit the local operating point excursion. Sieradzki [14] conducted an experimental campaign of a BLI fan to validate CFD results, showing some discrepancies for efficiency and stall margin reduction.

In our study, we started from indications provided in the literature to define an initial geometry that was manually refined until matching the optimisation requirements. The problem was faced through a series of simplifications enabling the use of standard design tools for axisymmetric inlet conditions. The outcome of the conceptual fan definition is described in Sec. VI, where the procedure and the comparison with different inflow profiles is reported.

IV. Propulsor Optimization: Two-Dimensional Design

The two-dimensional design phase has been carried out with the aim of finding a geometric configuration that could serve as a baseline for the 3D design. Such phase has consisted of three main steps:

- Propulsor geometric parametrization and definition of the design variables.
- Parametric analysis of the design variables influence on the performance metrics.
- Two-dimensional axialsymmetric shape optimization.

A. Geometric Parametrization

The parametric geometry has been generated by giving a high degree of freedom to the model. The design variables of such geometry, which is shown in Fig. 3, are: (a) the ratio between the aft fuselage length and the overall fuselage length L_{aft}/L_{fus} ; (b) the ratio between the highlight shroud radius and the fuselage maximum radius r_H/r_{fus} ; (c) the ratio between the intake axial length and the fan axial length L_{itk}/L_{fan} ; (d) the fan intake height h_I ; (e) the highlight shroud radius R_H ; (f) the highlight inclination angle α_H ; (g) the relative position of the cowl maximum radius point (x_A) normalized to the nacelle length; (h) the ratio between the exhaust and fan lengths L_{exh}/L_{fan} ; (i) the ratio between the fan exhaust and the fan intake areas A_E/A_I ; (j) the ratio between the fan exhaust and fan intake shroud radii R_E/R_I ; (k) the nozzle throat shroud radius R_N ; (l) the nacelle maximum thickness normalized to the nacelle length t_{nac}/L_{nac} ; (m) the shroud inclination angle at the nozzle section α_N ; (n) the plug curvature radius ρ_{plg} ; (o) the plug inclination angle β .

Fig. 3 2D Axisymmetric Geometric Parametrization.

The geometry is composed of different types of curve: the intake hub section has been drawn using a parabolic arc. The aft-fuselage has been generated using a 5th degree polynomial curve, with the imposition of the first and second derivatives values at the highlight section, thus granting a C^2 class of continuity to the curves. Both the intake shroud lip and the outer cowl lip have been defined with Bézier curves. The outer cowl portion downstream the maximum

radius point is defined by a circular arc.

The exhaust section is composed of two 5th degree polynomials: the shroud section considers as boundary conditions the passage through the edges, as well as a zero curvature condition at both the edges, a zero inclination at the fan exhaust (E) section and an inclination α_N at the nozzle throat section. The hub curve conditions are the passage through the edges, zero inclination on both the edges, zero curvature at the fan exhaust section and a curvature at the nozzle throat correspondent to the plug circular arc curvature. The plug is composed of a circular arc and a straight line of inclination β .

B. Design Space Investigation

The high degree of freedom of the parametric geometry translates in a great amount of design variables. In an optimization-wise approach, to reduce the number of design variables is preferable in order to reduce the overall optimization computational effort. This because of two main reasons: (1) a design variable which features a low influence on the performance parameters would not take active part on the optimization; (2) the population size is a function of the number of design variables which participate in the optimization.

To determine the correlations between the propulsor performance metrics and the design variables, a first Design of Experiments (DoE) has been carried out on the parametric model. In particular, in order to assess the influence on the performance of both the intake and exhaust regions, it has been decided to divide the overall design variables in two blocks, correspondent to the intake dvs (listed from a to g in the previous paragraph), and exhaust dvs (from h to o). For each block, a parametric analysis has been produced.

For each DoE, a set of 600 individuals has been defined based on a Latin Hypercube Sampling[15, 16], having determined appropriate side constraints to the dvs. For the intake DoE, the exhaust dvs have been fixed to the mean values between their respective side constraints. Vice versa, the intake dvs have been fixed at their mean values when considering the exhaust DoE. For both the design space investigations, a further design variable which has been considered is the fan total pressure ratio.

Figs. 4 and 5 show the results of the two Design of Experiments for the intake and exhaust dvs respectively, in terms of correlation plots: each row represents a design variable, whilst the columns show the forces acting on the various portions of the airframe, the Net Assembly Force, the fan shaft power and the ΔNAF efficiency. The circle dimension and color intensity represent the coupling level between parameters: the red color corresponds to a positive correlation, while the blue color corresponds to a negative one.

Fig. 4 2D Axisymmetric Design of Experiments results: intake design variables.

From the correlation plots, it is rather apparent how different degrees of correlation have to be expected from

Fig. 5 2D Axisymmetric Design of Experiments results: exhaust design variables.

each design variable, both for the NAF components and performance parameters. In particular, considering only the performance metrics (NAF , $\eta_{\Delta NAF}$), the most influential dvs concerning the intake DoE are: (a) the fuselage radius at the highlight section (r_H/r_{fus}); (b) the intake height (h_I); (c) the highlight shroud radius (R_H) and the fan total pressure ratio. Concerning the exhaust dvs, the most influential variables are the nozzle contraction ratio (A_N/A_E) and the fan total pressure ratio.

Fig. 6 shows the cumulative plot of both the design space explorations in terms of ΔNAF efficiency against the ΔNAF force coefficient, defined as:

$$C_{f,\Delta NAF} = \frac{\Delta NAF}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_{\infty}V_{\infty}^2 c_{mean}^2} \quad (10)$$

Such plot is in line with the qualitative map determined in a previous design space investigation[9] for the WTT model previously mentioned. Similar conclusions can therefore be drawn: (a) the points cloud feature the presence of a ‘maximum efficiency’ region: it is in fact quite apparent how larger values of required Net Assembly Force, i.e of the $C_{f,\Delta NAF}$ imply a penalization in terms of efficiency.

A further step has been made, by taking the best individuals of the two DoEs and merging their respective design variables. Furthermore, a reduction of the nacelle maximum thickness from 10% to 8% of the nacelle length has been considered. CFD evaluations of the performance of the new individuals have been done, and the results are expressed in Table 1. The fan pressure ratio of the two starting individuals is very similar, approximately of 1.345. It is interesting to note that the merged individual features an increasing in terms of efficiency. A further increasing in the ΔNAF efficiency is observed by reducing the nacelle maximum thickness.

Individual	Itk best	Exh best	Merged $th_{10\%}$	Merged $th_{8\%}$
$\eta_{\Delta NAF}$ []	0.7111	0.6973	0.7486	0.7584

Table 1 Design of Experiments: Performance evaluation.

Fig. 6 2D Axisymmetric Design of Experiments results: cumulative plot.

C. Two-Dimensional Optimization

The outcomes of the design space investigation served as basis for: (1) the definition of the most influential design variables to be used in the optimization process, as well as their side boundaries; (2) the determination of the baseline configuration, which has been produced by combining the design variables which granted the maximum efficiency of each parametric study.

As for the baseline individual, the choice has been to take as reference the one defined by merging the best individuals of each DoE, with the decreased maximum thickness of 8%. The DoE also served for the determination of the optimization design variables. From the intake correlation plot, it is apparent how the intake length and the outer cowl maximum radius point axial position have low influence on NAF and $\eta_{\Delta NAF}$. Still, they determine the external cowl shape, hence the possibility to control the occurrence of supersonic regions at the outer cowl. It has therefore decided to keep these design variables as constant. The same observation has been made for the exhaust DoE dvs which determine the outer cowl shape, hence the exhaust length and the nozzle throat shroud radius. It has been decided to fix the design variables which guide the fan exhaust area (A_E/A_I and R_E/R_I) for two main reasons: the main objective of the optimization is the maximization of the airframe performance, whilst the above-mentioned dvs take place in the fan design. It has also been decided to fix the nozzle shroud inclination angle at the throat and the tail plug inclination angle, being their influence on the performance parameters relatively low.

The optimization process has been carried out using GeDEA-II[17–23], a proprietary genetic algorithm which treats the genetic diversity as an objective, in order to emphasize both the most genetically different solutions and the non-dominated ones.

Being the main objective of the optimization the maximization of the ΔNAF efficiency, such figure of merit has been taken as one of the fitness functions. The cumulative plot of Fig 6 shows how different optima can be obtained at different ΔNAF values. Being the ΔNAF a surrogate of the net propulsive thrust, it can be treated as a performance requirement in terms of design. It becomes quite apparent that, in an optimization point of view, a wise choice should be determining the best individual in terms of $\eta_{\Delta NAF}$ for each NAF value. This has been done by defining as a second fitness function the Net Assembly Force: this choice permits to explore different NAF configurations simultaneously. The best individuals, lying in the Pareto Front, should therefore represent the highest efficiency configurations for each required NAF . The Multi-Objective Optimization Problem (MOOP) has been therefore formalized as in Eq. 11.

$$\text{minimize } \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{dv}) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1/\eta_{\Delta NAF} \\ NAF \end{array} \right\} \quad (11)$$

The results of the 2D optimization are presented in the objectives space - which has been normalized with reference on the maximum efficiency and Net Assembly Force module values - as in Fig. 7. The Pareto front clearly shows the

antagonist trend between the Net Assembly Force and the ΔNAF efficiency: higher efficiencies are observed for lower NAF cases. As optimal individual for the three-dimensional design, it has been chosen the one featuring the maximum ΔNAF efficiency. hence the individual in the Pareto Front which also corresponds to the minimum NAF .

Fig. 7 Normalized Pareto Front of the 2D optimization.

Fig. 8 shows the optimized 2D nacelle geometry and the correspondent isentropic Mach number, evaluated as:

$$M_{is}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{k-1} \left[\left(\frac{p_{ref}^0}{p(x)} \right)^{\frac{k-1}{k}} - 1 \right]} \quad (12)$$

with p_{ref}^0 evaluated as the stagnation pressure of the nacelle for the intake and external cowl profiles, and as the fan exhaust total pressure for the exhaust profile.

Fig. 8 2D Optimum: Nacelle shape and Isentropic Mach Number.

From the isentropic Mach profiles, the following observation can be made: (1) the optimization process led to a thin nacelle (the maximum thickness is the 8% of the nacelle length), and the maximum isentropic Mach number is lower

than unity, thus preventing the occurrence of a supersonic region at the outer cowl; (2) the intake section isentropic Mach number profile tends to smoothly settle at a constant value, therefore a diffusion upstream the fan is not observed; (3) the exhaust isentropic Mach number is lower than unity. Observing the Mach number contour of Fig. 9, it is apparent how the nozzle does not operate in choking conditions. A small supersonic region is observable downstream the nozzle section, due to a further flow expansion at the tail plug.

Fig. 9 2D Optimum: Mach number contour and stream function.

V. Propulsor Optimization: Three-Dimensional Design

In the optics of a full design, the the optimal individual has been taken as baseline for the three-dimensional refinement process. Such design phase has been carried out in two main steps:

- 1) A parametric analysis on the influence of the upsweep on the performance metric has been carried out, by considering a fixed axisymmetric shape for the propulsor, which is equal to the optimal one found in the 2-dimensional optimization;
- 2) A complete three-dimensional optimization of the propulsor shape has been carried out, by refining the profiles at appropriate azimuth planes, as well as the interpolation laws between such profiles.

A. Upsweep Parametric Analysis

The preliminary optimization has been carried out in axial symmetric conditions, therefore both the fan inlet flow distortion and the external flow do not feature any circumferential distribution. A complete three-dimensional design cannot preclude the presence of an aft-fuselage upsweep, therefore the primary concern has been to determine the influence of such design parameter to the airframe performance. It has therefore decided to preliminarily fix the propulsor shape and produce a parametric analysis on the upsweep. The design variable defining the upsweep has been considered in terms of slope ξ of the line connecting the first and last aft-fuselage cross section centres, as sketched in Fig. 10. Such variable has been normalized between 0 (which corresponds to an axisymmetric case) and 1 (which corresponds to the slope of the aft-fuselage that has been fixed during the WTT model design[10]).

Fig. 10 Upsweep parametrization.

The aft-fuselage curves have been generated using 5th degree polynomials with tangency and curvature conditions to the optimal intake hub shape: the choice has been made in order to maintain the same curves topology of the 2D parametric model. A loft surface has been therefore produced via parametric macro in CATIA[®].

Two parametric analyses have been carried out on the same population, which consisted in 6 equispaced samples from $\xi_{ax} = 0$ to $\xi_{max} = 1$. The first analysis has been done by fixing the ingested mass flow rate to the one of the two-dimensional optimum. The second parametric analysis considered the fan performance (fan total pressure ratio, polytropic efficiency) as constant. The results are presented in Fig. 11. The red lines represent the constant mass flow rate analysis, whilst the blue ones are referred to the constant fan analysis. The results showed that:

- By fixing the ingested mass flow rate, a decreasing in the fan total pressure ratio is appreciable. Having fixed the exhaust total temperature, the polytropic efficiency decreases. This results in an increasing of the fan shaft power. At the same time, the net assembly force tends to decrease, thus producing a drop in the ΔNAF efficiency.
- By fixing the fan total pressure ratio and polytropic efficiency, by increasing the upsweep it's possible to note an increasing in the mass flow rate, which translates in an increasing in the fan shaft power. It is worth noting that the fan shaft power increasing is lower than the one of the constant-mass flow rate case. The increasing in the mass flow rate also produces an increasing of the Net Assembly Force, due to the higher gauge force difference between the fan exhaust and intake sections. Such increasing tends to flatten for higher upsweep values, thus producing a maximum value to the ΔNAF efficiency at $\xi \approx 0.6$.

Fig. 11 Upsweep parametrization: results.

B. Three-Dimensional Propulsor Refinement

The parametric analysis of the aft-fuselage upsweep led to the choice of the $\xi_{opt} = 0.6$ configuration, while maintaining the same fan pressure ratio of the axisymmetric optimum. In order to maximize the ΔNAF efficiency for the given aft-fuselage configuration, the further step has been the optimization of the propulsor shape.

In order to achieve an optimal three-dimensional shape, it has been decided to define three propulsor azimuthal profiles, correspondent to the $0deg$, $90deg$ and $180deg$ azimuth planes. The design process started with assuming that the optimized axisymmetric propulsor should consist in the profile at the $90deg$ azimuth plane. Thus, the choice has been to refine the optimal shape for the azimuthal profiles at 0 and $180deg$. In this process, the majority of the 2D design variables have been constrained: the exhaust axial length, as well as the nozzle throat (area, inclination of the shroud surface, overlap, hub radius) have been set to the 2D optima values, whilst the target of the shape refinement have been the highlight height and the axial position of the cowl maximum radius point (x_A). The fan total pressure ratio has been also constrained to the axisymmetric optimum value.

Azimuthal interpolation laws have been also introduced, with the aim of connecting the three profiles. Being the propulsor shape substantially axial symmetric, with the exception of the highlight and the external cowl, the azimuthal laws which have been introduced are: (a) the highlight circumferential profile; (b) the x_A circumferential law.

The highlight section has been parametrized using two Bézier curves, which define two portions of the section (from 0 to $90deg$ and from 90 to $180deg$). For both the sections, the constrained points correspond to the curve ends, in which the azimuth values and the highlight radii are known. The central control points have been defined so that they could grant continuity with tangency between the adjacent curves. Therefore, considering the sketch of Fig. 12a, P_{1U} and P_{2L} have been freed to move horizontally, whilst P_{2U} and P_{1L} have been freed vertically.

The maximum cowl radius point interpolation law consists in a polynomial curve, as sketched in Fig. 12b. The curve boundary conditions are: (a) the passage through the points at azimuth 0 , 90 $180deg$; (b) zero derivative conditions at the azimuth planes 0 , $180deg$; (c) zero curvature at the azimuth planes 0 , $180deg$; for a total of 7 conditions, thus leading to a 6th degree polynomial. The resulting geometry is represented in Fig. 13.

A total of 8 design variables have been defined: two for each azimuth profile (highlight height and axial position of the max radius point), and two for each highlight Bézier curve. The design variables have been scaled so that each variable assumes zero value when corresponding to the baseline value. As baseline, the axial symmetric propulsor case has been considered. Having defined the highlight section in terms of Bézier curves, the axial symmetric condition will therefore be approximated by a set of control points which could best fit the circumference.

The optimization process has been carried out by analogy on the two-dimensional one: the MOOP has been formalized by using the formulation of Eq. 11. GeDEA-II has been used as optimization algorithm. The results are presented in Fig. 14, in the objective space, normalized against the baseline performance (which is highlighted with a star marker in the coordinates $[1, 1]$).

Fig. 12 Propulsor azimuthal interpolation laws.

Fig. 13 Three-Dimensional parametric geometry

It is apparent how the points tend to align in the objective space, determining a coupling between the two fitness functions. This trend is justified by having fixed the fan total pressure ratio and the nozzle contraction ratio. Such parameters are the most influential on the Net Assembly Force, because they guide the variations of the ingested mass flow rate and the fan Δp , thus producing a variation of the fan Δ gauge force components. Having fixed these design variables to the 2D optimum values, minor variations in the mass flow rate are observed, and mostly due to the small variations in the highlight area. Therefore, the fan shaft power tends to settle to very similar values for each individual.

On the other hand, any increasing in the Net Assembly Force is mostly due to the reduction of the airframe wall forces. Being the fan shaft power approximately constant through the population, it becomes quite clear how any increasing in the Net Assembly Force will translate in an increasing in the ΔNAF efficiency, by means of reducing the drag-components of the axial force. As optimal individual, it has been chosen the one featuring the highest ΔNAF efficiency, which settles around $\eta_{\Delta NAF} \approx 0.789$. The optimal geometry is presented in Fig. 15.

Figures 16 to 18 show the optimized nacelle profiles at the different azimuth planes, as well as the isentropic Mach number profiles. It is apparent that the major differences concern the $0deg$ profile, both in terms of highlight height and axial position of the maximum radius point. In particular, the highlight height is lower than the one at the $90deg$ azimuth plane, and the maximum radius point features a displacement towards the trailing edge. This is justified by considering the correspondent isentropic Mach profile: at the $0deg$ azimuth plane, the profile is invested by a faster flow. A displacement of such point downstream prevents the occurrence of a supersonic region at the external cowl lip, by

Fig. 14 Normalized Pareto Front of the 3D optimization.

Fig. 15 3D shape refinement: optimal individual.

flattening the isentropic Mach profile. Such flattening is not observed in the $90deg$ profile (Fig 17), which however features a maximum isentropic Mach number lower than unity.

Considering the $180deg$ profiles, a low increasing in the highlight height is observed. At the same time, the axial position of the maximum radius point is similar to the one of the baseline - $90deg$ - profile.

Fig. 16 3D Optimum: profile shape and Isentropic Mach number at azimuth 0deg.

Fig. 17 3D Optimum: profile shape and Isentropic Mach number at azimuth 90deg.

Fig. 18 3D Optimum: profile shape and Isentropic Mach number at azimuth 180deg.

VI. Conceptual Aerodynamic Fan Design

Starting from the results of the BLI360 optimisation, a conceptual design study for the fan rotor was carried out. The flow field on the Aerodynamic Interface Plane (AIP), located on the fan face, is highly nonuniform due to the non-axisymmetric boundary layer growth through the upswept fuselage. This gives rise to a distortion of total pressure, axial velocity, and static pressure, as illustrated in their AIP distributions of Fig. 19. The flow in the upper part is characterised by a higher radial total pressure gradient, associated to a larger axial velocity change from hub to shroud. The lower part has a more even profile, with a lower peak velocity at the tip.

Fig. 19 AIP distributions of fan inflow variables.

In the conceptual fan design, an aerodynamic model aiming at providing the required mass flow and fan pressure ratio as derived in the optimisation was investigated. The presence of such non-uniformity makes the process more challenging, as the adequacy of typical tools rely on a clean inflow is questionable. Instead, spoiled inlet conditions require capturing the blade interaction with the distorted region by simulating the unsteady propagation of the flow field through the rotating blades. These unsteady RANS simulations are far from being affordable on a daily basis for design purposes. Therefore, given that the scope of the activity was not a complete fan design study, requiring extensive investigation of aerodynamics and aeromechanics at full operating regime, but rather a conceptual definition of a blade geometry targeting the requirements, the problem was reduced to a simpler formulation according to some simplifying assumptions. In this manner, the use of standard analytical models was restored.

The workflow for the fan blade definition was based on a common and well-known approach relying on successive increment of dimensionality and complexity, from 0D mean-line (ML) to 2D vortex design. Figure 20 schematises the workflow, highlighting the inputs to the procedure and the various outputs. The boundary conditions and the fan design point (DP), expressed in terms of mass flow rate and fan pressure ratio, were provided from the 3D CFD simulation of the optimised configuration. In order to enable the adoption of mean-line analysis and axisymmetric radial equilibrium equation, the radial-azimuthal inlet field was circumferentially averaged to obtain the inflow profile. This equates to neglecting the different radial distribution seen by the blades as they rotate, assuming that the circumferential average can represent the average working condition of the row. Moreover, any upstream flow redistribution and the consequent swirl distortion are neglected. Clearly, such assumptions are quite strong, given the level of unevenness, but yet they restore proper conditions that can be handled by mean-line analysis. Mean-line was used to determine the main cascade parameters, based on the choice of work and flow coefficients. With the radial profiles of velocity and total pressure and the vortex distribution, the velocity triangles along the span could be determined. Finally, the selection of blade profiles and metal angles brought to the 3D blade definition. For a given geometry, single-passage steady-state RANS simulations were run to measure the performance and check the match of the DP specification. After a few iterations, a satisfactory agreement was found and the geometry was finalised.

The last part of the analysis was devoted to obtain an estimation of the full-wheel performance under the specific DP inlet distribution. This was carried out by combining a series of axisymmetric inflows results from steady CFD and applying the parallel compressor approach. The final output was a series of characteristic maps and an approximate estimation of the average operating point of the cascade.

The main features of the rotor, including the DP specification of TPR and mass flow rate are reported in Tab. 2.

The 3D blade stacking was formed by considering the circumferential average inflow profile, shown in Fig. 21. Due to the skewed shape of the axial velocity, the increase of the relative velocity towards the tip is compensated by

Fig. 20 Workflow for the conceptual fan design.

Table 2 Fan design point requirements and features of the selected geometry.

Quantity	Value
DP \dot{m} [kg/s]	253.7
DP FPR	1.343
DP η_{iso}	≥ 0.887
Fan diameter [m]	1.22
Hub/Tip ratio	0.425
Rel. Tip Mach no.	1.26

the recovery of momentum, resulting in a flat incident relative flow angle β_1 and low blade twist. The selected vortex design was close to a free vortex, with endwall corrections to account for the low hub momentum and high tip incidence variation.

Fig. 21 Inflow profiles at different azimuthal positions.

Fig. 22 Azimuthal sectors used to evaluate the fan performance through the discretised inlet.

The resulting three-dimensional blade was simulated solving steady-state single passage RANS equations. The verification of the rotor performance was carried out by comparing two data: the characteristic curve obtained with the circumferential average inflow used for the blade design, and the average operating point estimated by combining the performance with other spanwise axisymmetric profiles extracted at constant azimuthal positions. This latter approach represents a sort of parallel compressor discretisation, where the AIP is divided in four sectors of 90° extension, each having a spanwise distribution constant along the azimuth, as shown in Fig. 22. Because of this radial variation, each sector is assigned a characteristic curve computed under the axisymmetric assumption, differently from the original PC approach, where the speedline remains the same, since the inflow is uniform inside each sector. The overall operating point is estimated by a weighted average of the operating point of each sector, according to their extent, under the hypothesis of equal discharge static pressure [24].

The characteristic maps obtained are reported in Fig. 23, together with the clean speedline. The 0° TPR curve is close to the clean condition, while the circumferential average curve has a higher choking mass flow. The stall TPR remains similar for the three cases. Progressing towards areas of larger distortion, the deviation from the circumferential average enlarges, especially for the 180° curve, where the choking mass flow is 4% higher and the total pressure rise is 3% lower in absolute terms. In terms of isentropic efficiency, the peak value remains quite even and around 92%, above the design point target.

The mass flow and TPR requirements coming from the optimisation are slightly exceeded. At the design TPR, the mass flow is 6% in the circumferential average curve. However, the mass flux is expected to decrease when the fan operates in stage with the outlet guide vanes (OGV), where the nonuniform rotor exit conditions are likely to degrade the performance.

On each curve, an operating point is marked with a symbol. It represents the working point if the engine at a static pressure equal to the one giving the design TPR for the circumferential average profile. It can be observed that these points are aligned along a straight line. For this reason, the averaged operating point coincides with the one obtained with the circumferential average inflow. This result partially validates the choice of designing the fan blade using the circumferential average distribution. However, it still represents a crude estimation of the real working condition, since many effects are neglected, as already pointed out [25]. Therefore, additional investigations with higher fidelity methods are needed to verify the real fan performance.

Fig. 23 Inflow profiles at different azimuthal positions.

VII. Conclusions

The present work describes the optimization activities carried out for the definition of an optimized propulsive fuselage BLI system, based on a momentum conservation approach for the performance evaluation. The optimization process has been followed by a conceptual design of the fan which should operate at the nominal operating point conditions.

The nacelle design has followed different steps, starting from a parametric analysis and sequential optimization of a two-dimensional geometry. The result has been taken as a baseline for the three-dimensional shape refinement. Although the two-dimensional analysis has been considered in the preliminary design phases, it is relevant and consistent with the boundary layer ingestion physics, therefore it has given some insight on the performance metrics behavior:

- The nozzle contraction ratio plays a significant role in the propulsor performance: in particular, the 2D optimization led to a geometric configuration which favoured a high value of such variable. This is justified by the fact that such variable guides the ingested mass flow rate, therefore an increasing in the contraction ratio produces an increasing in the ingested mass flow, which translates in an enhancement of performance in terms of efficiency $\eta_{\Delta NAF}$.
- Short nacelles are favoured by the optimization, most likely because reducing the axial length reduces the external cowl wetted area, which in turn reduces the nacelle drag contribute.

The three-dimensional refinement showed two main outcomes:

- The highlight height is an increasing function of the azimuth angle, from 0 to 180deg.
- The outer cowl maximum radius point at the 0deg azimuth plane tends to settle downstream. This prevents the occurrence of a supersonic region at the external cowl lip: at such azimuth plane, the profile is locally less submerged, thus being invested by a faster flow. As a consequence, the outer cowl maximum isentropic Mach number tends to increase with respect on the 90deg profile. The displacement of the maximum radius point axial position is therefore justified by the tendency of decreasing the maximum isentropic Mach number.

The conceptual fan design based on the inputs of the optimisation employed the circumferential average inflow profile to select the blade features. The mean operating point estimated by averaging the results with different axisymmetric azimuthal inlets fell close to the condition used as reference design point and satisfied the requirements of mass flow rate and fan pressure ratio. A more faithful examination of the real blade performance, removing some of the simplifying hypotheses made, will be carried out using unsteady simulations that capture the distortion transfer and its interaction

with the rotating blades.

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